

CAPITAL MARKET AND DYNAMIC ADAPTATION MODEL: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

This study contributes to the capital market literature with a systematic literature review focused on the Dynamic Adaptation Model. The database used only focuses on journals indexed by Scopus in 2024. The sample in this study consists of 183 research articles. This study uses quantitative and integrative analysis, and reveals complex network associations, and detailed research trend analysis. This study contributes to the capital market literature by utilizing a robust and accurate methodology—the integration of bibliographies, also considering academic journals, using a broader range of keywords, and not enforcing any limitations related to the field of knowledge, thereby increasing the contribution of existing literature by allowing insights from more high-quality peripheral studies on the subject. The conclusions of this study are significant for researchers, investors, regulators, and the academic community in general. This study provides a highly structured network and clear information for research and literature, for future studies on capital market investment. This study also presents valuable insights to understand the microstructure of the capital market better and provide useful information for regulators to regulate the capital market effectively.

Keywords: Capital Market, Efficiency, Dynamic Adaptation Model, Bibliometric Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The capital market has experienced rapid development and is considered a very popular investment asset among investors. Stock market efficiency is one of the most debated issues among investors and also among academics. In 1970, Eugene Fama proposed that efficient markets fully reflect available information. Since then, EMH has become one of the most researched areas in financial theory. Due to the implications of the Efficient Market Hypothesis in financial markets, there is still constant scrutiny in this field. Over the past five decades, many studies have been conducted to test the validity of the EMH in various stock markets and different results have been found. A well-known debate in finance is between the followers of the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) and the supporters of behavioral finance; EMH states that markets are efficient, but behavioral finance argues otherwise (Malkiel, 2003). Lo, (2004) developed the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH), which states that EMH and behavioral finance are simply two sides of the same coin. According to the AMH, market efficiency changes over time, fluctuating between highly efficient and inefficient.

The AMH view of stock market efficiency has been widely studied. Mateus & Hoang, (2021) studied underdeveloped markets, Lim *et al.*, (2016) studied emerging and developed markets, and Urquhart, (2017) studied the most mature markets. Although market size is considered a significant factor in market efficiency (Kavussanos & Dockery, 2001), there is little research on AMH from a small stock market perspective. Several recent studies have shown that capital markets are not always efficient, especially in certain situations influenced by various external

and internal factors. Research on cryptocurrency markets, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, shows varying levels of efficiency depending on factors such as financial stress and the COVID-19 pandemic. During the pandemic, crypto markets exhibited significant inefficiencies, mainly due to high volatility and depressed market liquidity (Yadav, 2015); (Kakinaka & Umeno, 2022). The study emphasized that while some crypto assets approached efficiency, many others remained inefficient in responding to new information. On the other hand, studies on traditional capital markets also support similar findings. For example, some market anomalies, such as specific trading day effects or overreaction to new information, continue to occur in various global stock markets. A study by Akin & Akin, (2024) highlighted that investor bias and herd behavior remain major barriers to market efficiency in many developing countries. Furthermore, the effects of global crises such as pandemics also affect capital markets in developed and developing countries differently. The study shows that developed markets are more affected by the decline in global supply and demand, while emerging markets are more affected by domestic policy uncertainty (Taskinsoy, 2023). These studies collectively show that capital markets are often inefficient due to a variety of factors, including investor behavior, structural changes in the global economy, and technological limitations in processing information quickly and accurately.

Based on the research results and background, there is a great need to synthesize, combine, and identify literature gaps regarding the existing knowledge in the capital market literature in Developed and Developing Countries. Therefore, the researcher developed a systematic literature review on capital market structure. The objectives of this study are: 1) to consolidate and map the knowledge from the growing academic literature on capital market microstructure; 2) to facilitate future research by identifying literature gaps; and 3) to provide research results that are useful for investors, academics, researchers and regulators. This study contributes to the unconsolidated capital market literature, with a systematic literature review focused on capital market microstructure that reveals complex network associations, and detailed integrative analysis.

2. METHODS

This study presents a systematic review process. This study uses all literature related to the dynamic adaptation model since Lo first published his research in 2012, until now. This study uses all databases to search academic journals. The quality criteria selected for this study follow three main guidelines: 1) articles are English-language academic journals; 2) research discusses the topic of adaptive market hypothesis; and 3) research is included in the 2024 Scopus list. This study excludes all other studies that do not meet these criteria and as a result of this systematic review process, 63 research journals were obtained. This means that this research is still very small. The literature review was conducted using a systematic, explicit, and reproducible method (Garza-Reyes, 2015), or a mind mapping method that emphasizes the limits of knowledge. Bibliometric review is commonly used in scientific disciplines and focuses on quantitative studies of journals, books or other types of written communication (Heersmink *et al.*, 2011). Data were analyzed using bibliometric techniques based on the bibliometric analysis protocol from (Fahimnia *et al.*, 2015; Setyaningsih *et al.*, 2018) which

consists of: a) determining search keywords; b) obtaining initial search results; c) refining search results; d) collecting initial data, and e) analyzing data. Bibliometric techniques are used to represent the quantitative side of research results in the form of journal articles, books, or other types of written communication (Heersmink *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, to obtain more comprehensive analysis results, identification and grouping of article content was carried out based on objectives, variables, countries, and methodologies in MsExcel workbook format. This study is based on a structured or systematic review method with the aim of producing a systematic summary of various studies on investor belief and disposition effect. The structured review method used is based on two criteria to capture articles containing the topic of disposition effect. Determining the criteria aspect is what distinguishes it from conventional literature reviews. Some of the criteria used are:

- 1) Selection of appropriate and relevant keywords to search for articles in electronic databases. The keyword 'adaptive market hypothesis' is used to filter each article. This is done to ensure that the articles obtained are truly in accordance with the theme raised in this study, namely the adaptive market hypothesis.
- 2) The type of article selected for the data analysis process is to only use articles published by peer-reviewed international journals in English. This study does not use articles from conferences, theses, dissertations, or books on the grounds of ensuring the currentness of the study.
- 3) Articles from across fields or multi-disciplines are used to open up opportunities to obtain articles outside the fields of science and social sciences to increase the diversity of perspectives.

The first step in conducting a bibliometric analysis is to search for articles according to the topic of the adaptive market hypothesis. The process of searching for this article took 2 (two) months, with the help of Publish or Perish (PoP) software. This software was developed by Professor Anne Will Harzing from Tarma Research Software Pty Ltd-Melbourne (Bensman & Wilder, 2011). The database for the data collection process in this study used Google Scholar by considering aspects of accessibility and completeness of data sources. The keywords used were 'adaptive market hypothesis.' Then for further searches, the researcher determined that the title of the article must contain the words adaptive market hypothesis. In addition to these search conditions, other conditions, such as the year of publication, were used as criteria.

The analysis of this study used VOSviewer software (Almeida, 2021; Bartolacci *et al.*, 2020; Ding *et al.*, 2014; Galvao *et al.*, 2019; Heersmink *et al.*, 2011; Rialti *et al.*, 2019; Sadeghi Moghadam *et al.*, 2021). The researcher chose the bibliographic merging option because it combines articles based on the number of references shared (Bartolacci *et al.*, 2020; Ding *et al.*, 2014; Galvao *et al.*, 2019; Heersmink *et al.*, 2011; Rialti *et al.*, 2019; Sadeghi Moghadam *et al.*, 2021). This option allows for a very robust and accurate literature analysis, because it is based on the number of references where the relationship between articles does not change over time, unlike other options that are based on the number of citations where the relationship between articles may change over time (Bartolacci *et al.*, 2020; Ding *et al.*, 2014; Galvao *et al.*

al., 2019; Heersmink *et al.*, 2011; Rialti *et al.*, 2019; Sadeghi Moghadam *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the bibliography of coupling options in VOSviewer allows for rigorous replication of analyses (Bartolacci *et al.*, 2020; Caputo *et al.*, 2019).

3. BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

The search results with the keyword adaptive market hypothesis obtained 183 articles as initial data. The articles were published in the period from 2004 to 2024. This was done because the adaptive market hypothesis research in the field of finance was pioneered by Lo, (2004), the results of his research found the adaptive market hypothesis theory. The following are the results of journal data collection from Publish or Perish (PoP).

Table 1: Journal Data Collection Results

Indicator	Result
Query	Journal, <i>adaptive market hypothesis</i>
Source	Google Scholar
Years	2004-2024
Papers	183
Citations	5955
Cites/Year	297,75
Cites/Paper	32,54
Authors Paper	2,03
h_index	25
g_index	76
PoP hI norm	22
PoP hI annual	1,10

Note: The naming of the components in the indicator (e.g. query, source, etc.) still uses the English version according to the results of the PoP.

Based on table 1, it can be seen that the search process using PoP software produced 183 articles published over a 20-year period (2004 to 2024), with a total of 5955 citations or equivalent to 297.75 citations/year. After obtaining 183 articles, the article selection process was carried out so that 63 articles were published in reputable international journals.

As previously explained, the search process using PoP software produced 63 articles published over the period 2004 to 2024. All of these articles were then summarized into MsExcel format containing general information, such as title, author, year of publication, and journal specifications (journal name, tier, and publisher). In addition, for the needs of a more in-depth analysis to answer research questions, this study also uses specific information related to variables, perspectives, methodologies, and countries where the study was conducted. The results of the data collection used relevant journals, namely journals published in reputable journals (Q1 to Q4). The following is a picture of the distribution of articles published in the disposition effect per year, from 2004 to 2024. Figure 1 shows the number of publications on the Adaptive Market Hypothesis. 2020 was the year when more articles were published, totaling 11 Scopus-indexed articles. The following is Figure 1 regarding the number of publications from 2004 to 2024.

Figure 1: Number of Publications from 2004 to 2024

The results of the data collection show that the trend of Adaptive Market Hypothesis studies is still rarely carried out. From 2005 to 2008 there was no research on the Adaptive Market Hypothesis, but then in 2009 there was one article published. The number of articles published increased significantly in 2020, but then decreased again in 2021, then increased again in 2022, then decreased again in 2023 and increased again in 2024. Based on the publication sources, 63 articles reviewed came from international journals published by various leading publishers such as Emerald, SAGE, Wiley, and others. A total of 63 journals listed are top tier journals, which are classified in the Q1 to Q4 rankings by Scimagojr. Figure 2 shows the number of citations from 2004 to 2024.

Figure 2: Number of Citations from 2004 to 2024

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the highest number of citations was 2,600 citations in 2004. Based on the results of the number of citations from 2005 to 2024, it shows fewer citations, considering that old articles are more likely to have more citations. These results indicate a decrease in academic interest in researching the Adaptive Market Hypothesis. (Lo, 2004) is the most cited article with 2,600 citations, followed by Neely *et al.*, (2009) with 396 citations and Khuntia & Pattanayak, (2018) with 273 citations.

4. LITERATURE FINDINGS ON CAPITAL MARKET MICROSTRUCTURE

The final stage of bibliometric analysis is analyzing the data with the help of Mendeley software. This tool is used to manage the information needed in the analysis process, such as abstracts, keywords, and references. Data from Mendeley is then transferred into RIS format so that it can be processed by VOSviewer software.

This process is carried out to obtain keyword clusters (terms) and visualization maps that describe the flow of research in the field of Adaptive Market Hypothesis. The following are the visualization results based on keywords.

Figure 3: Visualization map based on keywords from all articles

Note: Color differences indicate clusters of common terms used

The following is a density map of keywords from all articles

Figure 4: Density map based on keywords from all articles

Note: Color differences indicate clusters of common terms used

Based on the data analyzed from 63 articles, it can be seen that some keywords that are relatively rarely used in the Adaptive Market Hypothesis research stream are the disclosure of the global Islamic stock market. Then other keywords also appear, namely bonds and cryptocurrency markers. In addition, there are still many other research opportunities regarding the Adaptive Market Hypothesis. This literature review discusses evidence supporting capital market inefficiency. Evidence shows that after an event, information is not immediately fully reflected in prices, thus implying inefficiency (Hashemi Joo *et al.*, 2020). Frazzini, (2006) stated that investors who hold loss stocks and realize gain stocks include market reactions (underreaction) due to news of company actions such as earnings announcements. Positive news will generally make prices appreciate, conversely, negative news will generally make prices depreciate.

Investors have a response to information, but cognitive abilities are limited in interpreting the information received so investors act naively, irrationally, and unsophisticated. Therefore, investors tend to base their behavior on rumors, issues, and speculation, and behave in mass behavior, impulsivity, loss-control, and impatience (Burns *et al.*, 1993). According to Burns *et al.*, (1993), information is used by investors as a consideration for making investment decisions. For investors, information is a signal that functions as a stimulus that influences the

cognitive process. Through the center of understanding information processing from cognitive, the mental investment process occurs in investors, so that the signal in the form of information can be considered good news or bad news. The manifestation of good news and bad news is a form of perception of expected values (return) and risk and shows investor attention in determining the decision to buy, hold, or sell shares. Good news or bad news causes buying or selling activities that can increase or decrease stock prices quickly (Bao et al., 2019; Barber et al., 2007; Q. Chen et al., 2007; Gârleanu & Pedersen, 2018; Merkley et al., 2017). When information is announced and all investors have received the information, investors first interpret and analyze the information as good news or bad news. The results of the interpretation of this information will affect investor demand and supply. Good news will make investors react positively so that investors will increase the number of stock purchases and will reduce stock supply in the capital market. Conversely, bad news is seen as a negative signal by investors, so investors will react negatively, namely by selling shares and increasing stock supply in the capital market. This will cause stock prices to fall (Sharpe *et al.*, 2005).

An inefficient capital market occurs when asset prices do not fully reflect available information, allowing for a difference between the market value and the intrinsic value of the asset. Recent evidence suggests a variety of situations in which capital markets are inefficient, supported by behavioral and structural factors. First, abnormal market volatility often reflects biased investor behavior. A recent study on the S&P 500 showed that behavioral factors such as overconfidence and loss aversion influence investor decisions. Overconfidence causes investors to overtrade, while loss aversion encourages them to hold on to losing assets for too long, resulting in market anomalies such as the disposition effect (Akin & Akin, 2024; Tan *et al.*, 2021). Second, the herding phenomenon, where investors follow trends without independent analysis, exacerbates inefficiencies. Herding can lead to price bubbles or market crashes that do not reflect economic fundamentals. This was especially evident during the 2022–2023 financial crisis, where investors collectively shifted their portfolios to safe-haven assets, creating pressure in equity markets (Woo *et al.*, 2020). Third, investor sentiment influenced by external factors such as geopolitical events and climate change also plays a major role. For example, the Russia-Ukraine conflict in 2022 increased global market uncertainty, causing a massive shift in investment preferences from stocks to commodities such as gold, even though commodity fundamentals did not change much (Peng *et al.*, 2023).

In addition, inconsistent monetary and fiscal policies contributed to market inefficiencies. During 2023, rapid interest rate changes by central banks caused uncertainty that affected market expectations, indicating a lack of efficient pricing mechanisms (Taskinsoy, 2023). In a behavioral context, short-term expectation bias has been shown to undermine market efficiency. Investors often focus more on short-term trends than on long-term fundamental value, as demonstrated by speculative buying patterns during the temporary uptrend in the technology sector in 2023. On the other hand, the influence of automated trading algorithms also poses a new challenge to market efficiency. Although designed to enhance efficiency, algorithms often amplify market volatility because their programs react simultaneously to small market changes, as observed in several flash crashes of 2022–2023 (Yadav, 2015). This evidence suggests that global capital markets remain vulnerable to behavioral and external

factors, which hinder efficiency despite continued technological and regulatory policy developments. The results of the study prove that there is inefficiency/efficiency of the capital market varies over time (Caporale *et al.*, 2018; Caporale & Plastun, 2019; Keshari Jena *et al.*, 2022). They revealed that there are still periods of inefficiency alternating with periods of efficiency, thus supporting the Adaptive Market Hypothesis (AMH) (Chu *et al.*, 2019; Duan *et al.*, 2021; Le Tran & Leirvik, 2020; Mensi, Al-Yahyaee, *et al.*, 2019; Mensi, Lee, *et al.*, 2019; Mensi, Rehman, *et al.*, 2019; Noda, 2021; Vidal-Tomás, 2021). For example, evidence reveals that the capital market presents multifractality and long memory properties, thus proving inefficiency; However, it is revealed that this inefficiency varies over time (Al-Yahyaee *et al.*, 2020; Charfeddine & Maouchi, 2019; Khuntia & Pattanayak, 2018). Furthermore, the calendar effect in the stock market also varies over time. Furthermore, evidence highlights that when the stock market faces a downturn, inefficiency appears to be higher; however, when the market rises, the level of inefficiency appears to decrease. This fact highlights that the level of inefficiency varies over time (Mensi, Al-Yahyaee, *et al.*, 2019; Mensi, Lee, *et al.*, 2019; Mensi, Rehman, *et al.*, 2019), thus supporting the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH).

The literature on investors in the stock market reveals that despite the presence of different age groups, genders, and trading patterns in stock trading, males are the dominant gender. They trade more frequently, hold shorter positions, and earn lower returns (Hasso *et al.*, 2019). Investors appear to pay more attention to news and high-rated stocks in all market phases (Subramaniam & Chakraborty, 2020). Further evidence suggests the existence of psychological barriers in the capital market, which show the strongest signs of psychological barriers (Fonseca *et al.*, 2020). In addition, it was also revealed that easy-to-read whitepapers are more attractive to investors.

5. CONCLUSION

From the explanation of capital market inefficiency, it can be concluded that the global financial market often does not meet the assumptions of the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH). Behavioral factors such as overconfidence, herding behavior, and loss aversion significantly affect asset price movements, creating long-lasting market anomalies. In addition, the influence of external sentiment, such as geopolitical events and inconsistent monetary policies, exacerbate market instability. Although technological developments such as trading algorithms aim to improve efficiency, they often actually increase volatility in certain market conditions. This inefficiency indicates that financial markets do not always reflect information perfectly. Future research needs to further explore the impact of trading algorithms on market volatility in various scenarios, including geopolitical situations and extreme market conditions. This analysis is important for creating a regulatory framework that can mitigate the risk of flash crashes. Additional studies are needed to evaluate how monetary policy uncertainty, especially during periods of interest rate tightening or loosening, affects asset price efficiency in the global market. Since behavioral factors play a major role in creating market anomalies, further research can focus on how investor biases differ across countries or cultures, and how these biases affect local and global markets. More effective regulation is needed to manage the systemic risks caused by algorithmic trading. This research should include the impact of new

rules on market liquidity and price stability. Further research on the relationship between external sentiments, such as climate change and pandemics, and market behavior will help understand patterns of market response to non-financial crises.

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